

REUNION ISLAND

a European living lab in the Indian Ocean

Research and innovation projects
funded by the European Union

Nexa

AGENCE RÉGIONALE DE DÉVELOPPEMENT
D'INVESTISSEMENT ET D'INNOVATION

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Biodiversity conservation and restoration

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BiodivERsA3

CONSOLIDATING THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA
ON BIODIVERSITY AND ECOSYSTEM SERVICES

- > European Program: **Horizon 2020**
Contract Number: **642420**
- > Coordinator: **The French Foundation for Biodiversity Research**
- > Local partner: **The Regional Council of Reunion Island**
- > Project Duration: **2015 - 2020**
- > **BUDGET**
Total cost: **37 967 427€**
Requested EC Contribution: **11 988 018€**

 www.biodiversa.org

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BiodivERsA is a network of national and regional funding organisations promoting pan-European research on biodiversity and ecosystem services, and offering innovative opportunities for the conservation and sustainable management of biodiversity.

The loss of biodiversity and degradation of ecosystems jeopardize the sustainable provision of ecosystem services and are major scientific and societal challenges. Addressing this challenge and providing scientific support to stakeholders and policy makers requires a coherent interdisciplinary research framework, with coordinated strategies and programmes at the national, regional and international levels, which are the relevant scales for many biodiversity issues.

By networking 32 funding agencies from 18 countries, BiodivERsA3 aims to strengthen the ERA on biodiversity. Building on the previous experiences of the projects (BiodivERsA1&2 and NetBiome), BiodivERsA3 promotes and support coordinated pan-European research on biodiversity and ecosystem services. It strengthens research and research programmes coordination with the ultimate aim to provide policy makers and other stakeholders with adequate knowledge, tools and practical solutions to address biodiversity and ecosystem degradation.

The objectives are to:

- Enhance the capacity of the network to coordinate research programmes on biodiversity and ecosystem services throughout all over in Europe (including

overseas territories) and to increase the international dimension of BiodivERsA activities.

- Develop a strategic, multi-annual vision of the network's priorities, based on ambitious mapping and foresight activities developed in collaboration with key initiatives in the field.

- Design and implement a co-funded call and other joint calls to better integrate research on biodiversity and ecosystem services across Europe.

- Develop a range of other joint activities, in particular, alignment of national research programmes for biodiversity and ecosystem services and activities for promoting mobility and equal opportunities for researchers and reinforcing data sharing.

- Promote effective science-policy and science-society (including science-business) dialogue during the whole research process.

BiodivClim

PROMOTING AND IMPLEMENTING JOINT PROGRAMMING TO REINFORCE TRANSNATIONAL RESEARCH AT THE CROSSROAD BETWEEN BIODIVERSITY AND CLIMATE CHANGE

- > European Program: **Horizon 2020**
Contract Number: **869237**

- > Project Duration: **September 2019**
August 2024

- > **BUDGET**
Total cost: **15 151 516€**
Requested EC Contribution: **5 000 000€**

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The biodiversity-climate change interaction is strong, bi-directional, and often positive (actions in favour of one are also beneficial to the other).

While the main drivers of biodiversity loss are habitat degradation, the syndrome of factors directly & indirectly associated with climate change is the dominant threat to biodiversity. It is therefore imperative to understand with sufficient detail and confidence the interactions between biodiversity & climate change so they can be incorporated into decision-support models & tools. By networking 33 funding agencies from 22 countries from Europe & other continents, BiodivClim aims to promote coordinated international research on biodiversity & climate change in all environments, incl. agricultural areas. It will strengthen research & research programmes coordination with the ultimate aim to provide policy makers & other stakeholders with adequate knowledge, tools & practical solutions to improve the conservation & sustainable use of biodiversity & ecosystems under a changing climate.

The BiodivClim objectives are to:

- Coordinate the research agendas of major European & international research funders to agree on shared research priorities related to biodiversity & climate change
- Reinforce collaboration with other relevant initiatives in the field to increase synergies & avoid fragmentation

- Design & implement two joint calls for research proposals in this field (incl. one co-funded)
- Promote research collaboration across national borders & disciplines in order to build capacity, exchange best practices & have a lasting effect on the international research community & landscape
- Support dialogue & collaboration between academia & stakeholders, and stakeholder engagement in research projects in order to increase the impact of research on policy & practice
- Ease rapid & efficient uptake of funded research results by the IPBES & IPCC for their future assessments, & by other relevant initiatives -Reinforce data open access.

Biodiv'om

PROTECTING THREATENED BIODIVERSITY IN FRENCH OUTERMOST REGIONS BY SUSTAINABLE AND DEMONSTRATION CONSERVATION ACTIONS

European Program: **LIFE**
Contract Number: **LIFE17 NAT/FR/000604**

Coordinator: **The French League for the Protection of Birds**

Local partners: **The Society of ornithological studies of Reunion, The National Park of La Réunion**

Project Duration: **2018 - 2023**

BUDGET
Total cost: **5 578 171€**
Requested EC Contribution: **3 269 634€**

Savane des Pères – Guyane © Florent BIGNON/LPO

The BIODIV'OM LIFE programme contributes to the conservation of five globally threatened species in the 5 European outermost regions.

The LIFE BIODIV'OM European programme has been established in order to protect the biodiversity of France's overseas territories: French Guiana, La Reunion, Martinique, Saint-Martin and Mayotte.

These overseas territories are home to 80% of France's biodiversity, a unique biodiversity in the world and exceptional at the European level. However, it is highly threatened on these small insular territories by an increasing human population and pressure from investment, forestry, mining and tourism as well as climatic events.

LIFE BIODIV'OM is necessary in order to limit the decline of biodiversity occurring in these 5 overseas territories. It follows on from the LIFE+ CAP DOM European programme that was coordinated by the LPO - (French League for the Protection of Birds) and concerned three French overseas territories: French Guiana, La Reunion and Martinique from 2010 to 2015.

This new programme aims at consolidating the useful links formed between the three territories during LIFE+ CAP DOM and to continue to conserve those birds and the French Guiana savannas. It includes two new territories: Saint-Martin and Mayotte and three new species: Atlantic goliath grouper, Nassau grouper and Madagascar pond-heron. This programme's prime aim is to assure the continuity of the actions and to favour less costly methods by involving local people.

The LIFE BIODIV'OM programme has two main objectives:

- Increase the populations of 5 global threatened species
- Improve the conservation of threatened species' habitats

Mérou de Nassau (Epinephelus striatus) © Stephen FRINK

Échenilleur de La Réunion - mâle (Lalage newtoni) © Jaime MARTINEZ

CAP DOM

CONSERVING FRENCH OVERSEAS THREATENED BIRD SPECIES AND THEIR HABITATS USING DEMONSTRATIVE CONSERVATION TOOLS

European Program: **LIFE**
Contract Number: **LIFE09 NAT/FR/000582**

Coordinator: **The French League for the Protection of Birds**

Local partner: **The Society of ornithological studies of Reunion, The National Park of La Réunion**

Project Duration: **2010 - 2015**

BUDGET
Total cost: **2 251 500€**
Requested EC Contribution: **1 111 650€**

<https://lifecapdom.org/>

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Cap DOM is a project on knowledge, management and protection of endangered bird species and habitats in Réunion, French Guiana and Martinique.

Though still accounting for 80% of French biodiversity, French outermost regions biodiversity has significantly declined in recent years. Biodiversity in these areas is threatened by invasive species, urbanisation and economic activities, as well as a lack of appropriate conservation tools. The Birds and Habitats Directives is not enforce in these regions and biodiversity protection is neither integrated into policies; such as agriculture, fishing or trade. Because of their remote geographical location, research developments and technical innovations in nature conservation have tended to overlook these regions. Furthermore, conservation management tools that have been developed for the European continent are not necessarily suitable for the outermost regions because of the specificities of the

local, natural and socio-economic contexts of the outermost regions..

The objective of this LIFE Biodiversity project was to contribute to stopping biodiversity loss in three French Outermost Regions (Reunion, Martinique and French Guiana), by testing demonstrative and innovative conservation management tools for the protection of threatened bird species and their habitats, and by disseminating the results to other EU overseas territories.

Coq de roche orange (Rupicola rupicola) - © G. Feuillet

Papangue mâle posé au sol - © Jean-François Bègue

CORCOPA

OPTIMIZED CONSERVATION OF
EUROPA'S CORAL REEFS USING
ECO-ACOUSTICS

European Program: **BEST 2.0**
Contract Number: **2266**

Coordinator: **The Entropie Joint Research
Group : tropical Marine Ecology of
Pacific and Indian Oceans, University of
Reunion Island**

Project Duration: **2018**

BUDGET

Total cost: **112 610€**
Requested EC Contribution: **99 620€**

 <https://umr-entropie.ird.nc/index.php/portfolio/projet-corcopa>

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CORCOPA aims at reinforcing and sustaining the technical capacities of the French Southern and Antarctic Lands Authorities for the management of the coral ecosystems of the Scattered Islands.

The CORCOPA Project sets up and implements an innovative, operational and inexpensive monitoring tool, adapted to both the isolation of Europa and the pace of change being experienced by its ecosystems. The eco-acoustic approach, which is booming worldwide, is based on the passive recording of the «soundscape» and its ecological interpretation. By coupling spot recordings of soundscapes and visual assessments of reef stands the project team is planning to define the links between the characteristics of ambient sound and the ecological status of associated stands on Europa's reefs in order to establish reference acoustic state. An autonomous underwater station is installed with the aim of performing and interpreting a continuous

monitoring-daytime and night-time - of the sound environment of Europa's reefs. Two major aspects of sound are studied: sound volume (SPL) and signal complexity (ACI), especially on frequency bands already identified as representative of the activity of certain reef organisms. The detection of marine mammals is also considered. The team also proposes to transmit to the TAAF (French Southern and Antarctic Lands authorities) a ready-to-use tool for non-specialists in the field of eco-acoustics to enable the long-term monitoring of biodiversity and ecosystem services and therefore contribute to better management.

DyCIT

THE DYNAMIC AND CONSERVATION OF THE ISLAND OF TROMELIN

European Program: **BEST 2.0**
Contract Number: **1180**

Coordinator: **The Entropie Joint Research Group : Tropical Marine Ecology of Pacific and Indian Oceans, University of Reunion Island**

Other local partner: **The Mascarin National Botanical Conservatory**

Project Duration: **2016 - 2018**

BUDGET

Total cost: **173 940€**
Requested EC Contribution: **96 000€**

[https:// umr-entropie.ird.nc/index.php/portfolio/projet-dycit](https://umr-entropie.ird.nc/index.php/portfolio/projet-dycit)

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The project main objective is to **Increase the understanding of the interactions, both positive and negative, between the island's marine birds, vegetation and mouse population to inform the management of the island and be used for other similar islands.**

DyCIT assess the dynamics of the small tropical island of Tromelin following the eradication of rats.

This is an essential aspect of the conservation of biodiversity and ecosystem services as the effects of an action must be assessed and quantified, including its temporal dimension, to inform effective management, reorient current actions and improve monitoring protocols. The learning from the project is also relevant for other similar island ecosystems, especially in the tropics.

The project focuses on the island's seabirds and vegetation to assess how they have evolved since the rat eradication, and following the introduced mouse population to understand its impact on the island's biodiversity and assess possibilities for eradication. The monitoring of these biological indicators produces information to future management actions for the island.

Fruit Bat

FEEDING ECOLOGY OF THE MAURITIUS FRUIT BAT, INTERACTIONS WITH FRUIT CROPS AND THE IMPLICATIONS FOR THE CONSERVATION OF THE SPECIES ON REUNION

European Program: **BEST RUP**

Coordinator: **The Chiroptera group of the Indian Ocean (GCOI)**

Project Duration: **2018 - 2019**

BUDGET
Requested EC Contribution: **49 789€**

The main objective of this project is to better understand the behaviours of the Mauritius Fruit Bat in La Réunion in order to determine appropriate conservation measures.

Fruit producers in Mauritius accuse the Mauritius Fruit Bat of destroying crops, thus the species is rather feared by fruit producers in Reunion. The current population in Reunion, of around 100 individuals, is gathered in a single site and thus extremely vulnerable to any disturbance.

The project is using GPS bio-loggers to track the movements of previously tagged individuals and combining this with in situ observations to determine the bats' feeding behaviours.

This information is shared with stakeholders in the local fruit sector and used to determine conservation measures adapted

to the conservation of the species on the island. Various communication actions are implemented to disseminate the results of this project to a wide audience

Photos : Groupe Chiroptères Océan Indien © Sarah Fourasté

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LIFE+ COREXERUN

CONSERVATION, RESTORATION AND RECONSTITUTION OF SEMI-XEROPHILOUS FOREST ON THE REUNION ISLAND

European Program: **LIFE**
Contract Number: **LIFE07 NAT/F/000188**

Coordinator: **The National Park of
Reunion Island**

Other local partner: **The French Coastal
protection agency**

Project Duration: **2009 - 2013**

BUDGET

Total cost: **2 571 548€**
Requested EC Contribution: **1 284 699€**

 www.lifecorexerun.fr/?p=1524

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The COREXERUN project aimed at ensuring the ecological viability of semi-xerophilous habitats in La Reunion

La Reunion is one of the world's top 25 hotspots for biodiversity. Scattered on the western part of the island, its semi-xerophilous forest habitats are unique. Although they have completely disappeared in other places of the Mascarenes, in La Reunion relics are estimated to cover just 1% of their original area of 56 800 ha. These last relics, however, are subject to high natural and human threats, and are only present today in a degraded form and in inaccessible areas, such as gullies and cliffs. The mountain range which contains around 255 ha of substandard semi-xerophilous habitat, provides an important example of vegetation in La Reunion. Today, the main threat is the rapid and uncontrolled growth of invasive species.

The COREXERUN project aimed to ensure the ecological viability of semi-xerophilous habitats in La Reunion. Specifically, it aimed to:

- Restore and preserve around 30 ha of domestic relic habitat that are subject to high anthropic and natural pressures, in order to ensure their ecological functionality;
- 9 ha of semi-xerophilous habitats on a small plateau between two gullies and resting on existing relics in order to potentially restore

an ecological corridor;

- Combat the erosion of biodiversity by preserving the unique species sheltered by these habitats through the reintroduction of flora species that are close to extinction, while avoiding the risk of genetic pollution;
- Define innovative protocols for the restoration and the reconstitution of semi-xerophilous habitats in La Reunion, which can be transferred to similar areas;
- Acquire greater knowledge of the semi-xerophilous habitats;
- Exchange experiences and raise awareness of the need to protect biodiversity, especially this type of habitat.

LIFE+ Forêt sèche

DRY FOREST CONSERVATION IN RÉUNION ISLAND

European Program: **LIFE**
Contract Number: **LIFE13 BIO/FR/000259**

Coordinator: **The National Park of
Reunion Island**

Local partner: **The French Coastal
protection agency**

Project Duration: **2014 - 2020**

BUDGET
Total cost: **2 852 003€**
Requested EC Contribution: **1 426 601€**

<http://www.foretseche.re/>

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The LIFE Forêt Sèche project aims at preserving unique semi-xerophilic forest habitats on Réunion Island and to re-establish the connectivity between restored and relict plots.

Semi-xerophilous (semi-dry) forest is one of the most emblematic habitats of Réunion Island. Today only about 1% of its original area of 56 800 ha remains, scattered in small plots across the western coast (Mafate and Cilaos cirques) and the La Montagne mountain range. The main causes of this regression include heavy demographic pressure, loss of connectivity between relict areas, invasive alien species, decline of native species, such as the Reunion Island day gecko, and the lack of awareness among the local population. Réunion National Park coordinated a previous LIFE project on semi-dry forests (LIFE07 NAT/F/000188 - COREXERUN), which committed the park and its partner to an ambitious conservation project to save the endangered forests. Results from that

project pointed out the need for low-cost restoration of greater areas to guarantee long-term conservation success.

The LIFE Forêt Sèche project aims to preserve unique semi-xerophilic forest habitats on Réunion Island and to re-establish the connectivity between restored and relict plots. It demonstrates that the long-term conservation of this habitat can be achieved at lower cost, with a reduction goal of 20%, by the implementation of innovative measures. To achieve this objective, a set of demonstration actions and innovative approaches is implemented in a coordinated and integrated manner. These actions aimed to directly and indirectly promote cost-effective conservation on a greater area of the semi-dry forest on Réunion Island.

LIFE+ Pétrel

HALTING THE DECLINE OF ENDEMIC PETRELS
FROM REUNION ISLAND: DEMONSTRATION
OF LARGE-SCALE INNOVATIVE CONSERVATION
ACTIONS

European Program: **LIFE**
Contract Number: **LIFE13BIO/FR/000075**

Coordinator: **The National Park of
Reunion Island**

Other local partners: **Society of ornitho-
logical studies of Reunion, National
office for hunting and wild animals, the
University of La Reunion, Indian Ocean
Nature Brigade**

Project Duration: **2014 - 2020**

BUDGET
Total cost: **3 100 500€**
Requested EC Contribution: **1 550 250€**

 www.petrels.re

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The LIFE + Petrels project aims at halting the decline of endemic petrels in Reunion, emblematic of Reunion Island's exceptional biodiversity.

Reunion is the only tropical island in the world to play host two endemic petrels. However, a lack of conservation measures to protect the endemic petrels will result to their extinction and will add-on the existing list of 22 extinct bird species of the island. This loss of biodiversity is not only a local ecological disaster, but also a worldwide disaster. For years, Reunion National Park has been working to protect these species with the Society of ornithological studies of La Réunion [SEOR], the National office for hunting and wild animals [ONCFS], the Indian Ocean Nature Brigade [BNOI], the University of La Reunion to rescue stranded petrels, organise the "Nights Without Lights" Campaign, to look for nesting sites in the island's mountains, and to monitor petrel colonies and populations. This is an emergency situation and two national action plans (NAPs) have already been set up (1. Mascarene Petrel NAP, 2012 and 2. Barau's Petrel NAP, 2008) in order to identify threats to the species and to undertake immediate actions to conserve them, including clearing rubbish and reducing numbers of wild predators (cats and rats) as well as levels of light pollution.

The projet develops and implements innovative strategies and conservation techniques in a highly urbanized island, and removes regulatory, technological and logistical barriers. It consults and involves stakeholders, reduces threats to the species and engages in conservation activities compatible with the island's economic development. These endangered endemic species are among the rarest seabirds in the world.

MOVE

FACILITATING MAES TO SUPPORT REGIONAL POLICY IN OVERSEAS EUROPE: MOBILIZING STAKEHOLDERS AND POOLING RESOURCES

European Program: **European Commission Directorate-General for Environment (ENV.D.2)**

Contract Number: **808239**

Coordinator: **The Regional Fund for Science and Technology (FRCT)**

Local partner: **The Espace DEV Joint Research group _ University of La Réunion**

Project Duration: **2018 - 2021**

BUDGET

Total cost: **1 060 781€**

Requested EC Contribution: **991 384€**

 <https://moveproject.eu/>

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The main objective of the MOVE project is to map and assess the state of ecosystems and their services in the Outermost regions (ORs) and Overseas countries and territories (OCTs) and to promote the involvement of decision makers.

MOVE pilot project intends to involve policy makers, researchers and the civil society in the development of methodologies for mapping and assessing the state of ecosystems and their services in ORs and OCTs.

A coordinated and synergistic approach is advocated to turn the geographical, political and knowledge base fragmentation of these entities into assets, pooling resources and building robust participatory tools.

The project will start by assessing the state of the art of the MAES (Mapping and

Assessing Ecosystem Services) exercise within the participating overseas regions, and by inventorying and motivating the human and material capacities present in each of them.

4 cases studies within the ORs and OCTs will be implemented.

In addition to producing a tangible contribution for the MAES exercise, this project aims to demonstrate the possibility and the added value of a bottom-up approach, involving and capacitating local actors.

MOVE-ON

FROM CASE STUDIES TO ANCHOR
PROJECTS-SETTING THE GROUND TO ADVANCE
MAES IN EUROPE'S OVERSEAS TERRITORIES

European Program: **European
Commission Directorate-General
for Environment (ENV.D.2)**

Contract Number: **776517**

Coordinator: **The Regional Fund for Science
and Technology (FRCT)**

Local partner: **NEXA, the regional agency
for development, investment and
innovation in Reunion Island**

Project Duration: **2020 - 2023**

BUDGET

Total cost: **1 499 282€**

Requested EC Contribution: **1 424 318€**

The project aims at mapping and assessing the state of ecosystems and their services in the outermost regions and overseas countries and territories.

The ongoing work on MOVE project through a consortium has already showed that the steps forward in the implementation of MAES in ORs and OCTs involve (i) tailoring existing methodologies, or develop new ones, taking into account common specificities and needs, (ii) providing opportunities for knowledge exchange and collaborative work and (iii) promoting the involvement of decision makers in initiatives with practical relevance. Therefore, the present action proposes to address these 3 issues in an integrated fashion.

The central feature of this proposal is the development of 4 Anchor Projects. These have multiple purposes. On a basic level they will advance MAES in a context of low development in the field. In this sense, they were chosen to cover a wide range of ecosystems (marine and terrestrial), geographical locations and scales, and to cover all the spectrum from methodological development to decision-maker advice. But the Anchor Projects are also opportunities for joint reflections on the methodological specificities of ORs and OCTs and as a focus were similar, ongoing initiatives could converge, creating synergies and opportunities for development at a scale larger than the initial consortium. Finally, they were planned to respond to specific needs of decision-makers, so they can

bridge the gap between the technical and the political spheres. This will be further aided by an Activity fully dedicated to looking at how the protection of environment and the improvement of the health status of ecosystems can support the achievement of EU and International policies and goals, developing and disseminating good practice guidelines and policy recommendations.

To support the Anchor Projects, a group of partners will review the existing methodologies and approaches, adapting them to the specificities of the EU Overseas. These regions have unique pristine ecosystems, and the opportunity will be taken to also develop conceptual models of ecosystem services provision changes according to the "quality" of the ecosystems in a context of climate change and anthropogenic pressures.

Outreach and sustainability are key and interrelated concerns, therefore MOVE-ON will also create an EU Overseas Ecosystem Knowledge Network which will focus in the work of researchers, technicians and decision-makers after the project ends.

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PRODVEGEUR

DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTONOMOUS PLANT PRODUCTION UNIT
FOR THE RESTORATION OF HABITATS AND THE BIOLOGICAL
REINFORCEMENT OF POPULATIONS OF PLANT SPECIES
ON THE ISLAND OF EUROPA

European Program: **BEST 2.0**

Contract Number: **2243**

Local coordinator: **The Mascarin National
Botanical Conservatory**

Project Duration: **2018 - 2019**

BUDGET

Total cost: **98 644€**

Requested EC Contribution: **98 644€**

The main objective of the project is to install a functional plant production unit on Europa to support ecological restoration operations and build the capacity of French Southern and Antarctic Lands authorities, in charge of the implementation of the overall environmental actions of the island.

The Island of Europa shows an exceptional state of conservation and is a veritable sanctuary of terrestrial and marine biodiversity providing scientists with an ideal open-air laboratory for understanding many evolutionary, ecological and ecosystem processes. The general objective of the project is the in situ installation of a functional plant production unit in an environment favorable towards an ecological restoration operation on Europa Island while transferring skills to the TAAF (French Southern and Antarctic Lands authorities) officers who are responsible for the management of the site. Following the reception of the seeds of native plant species harvested on Europa by

the conservation officers, training sessions on the propagation and rearing methods of these species are provided to the TAAF officers within the production unit of CBN-cpie Mascarin. A field mission on Europa will be undertaken to install the functional production unit and to control the exotic woody plants around the TAAF station so as to transform this space into area for the multiplication of the native plants for future ecological restoration operations.

<https://ileseparses.cbnm.org/>

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REPT'ILE

TERRESTRIAL REPTILES OF THE SCATTERED ISLANDS

European Program: **BEST 2.0**
Contract Number: **1173**

Coordinator: **Nature Océan Indien**

Project Duration: **2016 - 2017**

BUDGET

Total cost: **48 585€**
Requested EC Contribution: **48 585€**

The project main objective is to improve knowledge of terrestrial reptiles on the Glorioso islands, update assessment of the species conservation status and improve management measures.

This project aims at improving the knowledge and conservation of terrestrial reptiles on the Glorioso Islands and provide a baseline of the still little known herpetofauna. Through desk-based research and collation of existing data and field trips to Grande Glorieuse, Île du Lys and Roches Vertes it will assess (or reassess) the conservation status of all terrestrial reptiles.

The data collected for each species will be analysed and a summary will be produced. A Geographic Information System maps will also be produced for each species. The results of the project will be published in the form of a scientific paper.

https://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/biodiversity/best/pdf/fs_reptile_en.pdf

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Circular Economy

REPLACE ◊ SCREEN ◊ URBAN-WASTE

REPLACE

REGIONAL POLICY ACTIONS FOR CIRCULAR ECONOMY

European Program: **INTERREG Europe**

Coordinator: **The regional Council of Lazio Region, Italy**

Local partner: **NEXA, the regional agency for development, investment and innovation in Reunion Island**

Project Duration: **2019 - 2023**

BUDGET

Total cost: **31 694 570€**

Requested EC Contribution: **1 374 769€**

The project aims at improving the management, implementation and monitoring of regional policy instruments that aim at facilitating the transition towards a circular economy and boosting sustainable development.

Circular economy (CE) is very relevant for European projects, due to raw materials lack and environmental problems. REPLACE (Regional Policy Actions for Circular Economy) aims at integrating, deploying and capitalizing on lessons learnt through the Horizon 2020 project SCREEN (www.screen-lab.eu), by engaging policy makers and managing authorities with the common objective of improving Regional Operational Programmes (ROPs) and their performances in the field of Circular Economy, to be in line with the Circular Economy Action Plan of the European Commission.

The project aims at improving management, implementation and monitoring of regional policy instruments which are aiming at facilitating the transition towards a circular economy and boosting sustainable development: the overall objective is to create and apply policies and actions focusing on identification, valorisation, assessment and financing of circular value chains, and related project (local and interregional). In addition, a replicable framework for regional benchmark on circularity excellence level is proposed.

REPLACE wants to fulfil a synergic use of funding for circular economy, connected to RIS3, and enhance innovation,

competitiveness, economic and employment performances, while increasing effectiveness of policy instruments. REPLACE shared and integrated approach involves a significant amount of resources, both material (funds) and immaterial (know-how).

REPLACE has an innovative horizontal cross-cutting approach, not focusing on one or more specific aspects of the circular economy, but dealing with the lack of an effective and shared strategy for CE at regional level; it aims at introducing, in the regional policy instruments, measures able to increase cooperation among regions (targeted at financing cross-regional value chains).

www.interregeurope.eu/replace

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SCREEN

SYNERGIC CIRCULAR ECONOMY ACROSS
EUROPEAN REGIONS

- > European Program: **Horizon 2020**
Contract Number: **730313**
- > Coordinator: **The regional Council of Lazio Region, Italy**
- > Local partner: **NEXA, the regional agency for development, investment and innovation in Reunion Island**
- > Project Duration: **2016 - 2018**
- > **BUDGET**
Total cost: **1 742 748€**
Requested EC Contribution: **1 742 748€**

 www.screen-lab.eu/

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SCREEN has defined a replicable systemic approach towards a transition to Circular Economy in EU regions within the context of the Smart Specialization Strategy, thus contributing to novel future eco-innovative and horizontal business models across different value chains.

SCREEN aims at the definition of a replicable systemic approach towards a transition to Circular Economy in EU regions within the context of the Smart Specialization Strategy, through the identification and implementation of operational synergies between R&I investments from Horizon 2020 and the European Structural and Investment Funds, thus contributing to novel future eco-innovative and horizontal business models across different value chains.

The concept of the action is to develop a EU reference framework to establish operational synergies between Horizon 2020 and the

European Structural and Investment Funds related to Circular Economy by:

- Sustaining the regional actors' participation at Horizon 2020
- Encouraging the entrepreneurial initiatives based on Horizon 2020 project's results
- Investigating the possibility of maximizing the Horizon 2020 investment through a "recovery" (fully or partial) of well.

SCREEN network in a nutshell:

- 17 European Regions
- 12 European Countries
- +30 International and local workshops
- 6 Policy lab meetings
- +20 circular economy value chains
- +200 Ideas for research and development
- +20 Potential operational synergies
- +100 cross-regional funding synergies
- 9 Signed Memorandum of understandings and Letter of Intents

Figure 2: SCREEN network in a nutshell.

UrBAN-WASTE

URBAN STRATEGIES FOR WASTE MANAGEMENT
IN TOURIST CITIES

- > European Program: **Horizon 2020**
Contract Number: **690452**
- > Coordinator: **The government of the Canary Islands**
- > Local partner: **Agorah, the Agency for observation, development and housing of Reunion Island**
- > Project Duration: **2016 - 2019**
- > **BUDGET**
Total cost: **4 248 783€**
Requested EC Contribution: **4 248 783€**

The **URBAN WASTE** project aims at helping the development of strategies seeking to reduce the amount of municipal waste production as well as strategies to further develop the re-use, recycling, collect and the disposal of waste.

Europe's cities are some of the world's greatest tourism destinations. The socio-economic impact of tourism and urban tourism is extraordinary, but it brings at the same time a range of negative externalities, including high levels of unsustainable resource consumption and waste production. In comparison with other cities, tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and the specificity of tourism industry and of tourists as waste producers.

UrBAN-WASTE supports policy makers in answering these challenges and in developing strategies that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist

cities. In doing so UrBAN-WASTE adopts and applies the urban metabolism approach to support the switch to a circular model where waste is considered as resource and reintegrated in the urban flow.

UrBAN-WASTE performs a metabolic analysis of the state of art of urban metabolism in 11 pilot cities. In parallel a participatory process involving all the relevant stakeholders will be set up through a mobilization and mutual learning action plan. These inputs are integrated in the strategies along with a review of the most innovative existing technologies and practices in the field of waste management and prevention. The strategies are then to be implemented in the 11 cities and the results monitored and disseminated to facilitate the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes.

www.urban-waste.eu

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Energy Transition

ABC-21 ◊ e-SPACE monitoring ◊ REACT
◊ RESOR ◊ TRUST-PV ◊ LEAP-RE

ABC-21

AFRICA-EUROPE BIOCLIMATIC BUILDINGS FOR THE XXI CENTURY

- > European Program: **Horizon 2020**
Contract Number: **894712**

- > Project Duration: **September 2020**
August 2022

- > **BUDGET**
Total cost: **1 082 312,50€**
Requested EC Contribution: **1 082 312,50€**

 <https://www.abc21.eu/>

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Forecasts indicate that more than half of global population growth until 2050 will occur in Africa, and it will be followed by the expansion of housing and building needs.

This expansion in the building sector must be based on sustainable and energy efficiency principles to mitigate global warming. New buildings should be designed following concepts that will make them robust against expected climatic changes during their lifetime. But unfortunately, the manifestation of globalisation trends in building design resulted in the adoption of inadequate design solutions for warm climate regions, which performs poorly energy-wise.

In this context, it is urgent to study the best sustainable designs for warm climate zones to unleash their market and research potential, thus popularising these concepts to a broader audience. These designs involve bioclimatic approach, low-energy cooling techniques and the use of local construction materials, some of which already exist in Africa and only need to be identified and adapted. Inspiration for such techniques may come from Nature, such as the Saharan Silver ants that provide an elegant technical solution to stay cool in the sun with their enhanced optical reflection and radiative heat dissipation capabilities. Combining these next-generation approaches with the best bioclimatic solutions will be the hallmark of the ABC 21 project.

The objectives of ABC-21:

- Identify, report and strengthen BioClimatic designs and local materials in Africa and Europe
- Promote the exchange between Africa and Europe to enhance policy and regulations for low-cost and effective BioClimatic designs
- Support the development of certified sustainable and cost-effective building local materials and its supply chain
- Analyse the applicability of state-of-the-art of surface finishing's and future weather files in innovative bioclimatic solutions

e-SPACE monitoring

E-SOLAR PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS AND DATA
COLLECTION FOR ENERGY MONITORING

European Program: **Horizon 2020**
Contract Number: **734948**

Coordinator: **Reuniwatt**

Project Duration: **2016 - 2017**

BUDGET
Total cost: **71 429€**
Requested EC Contribution: **50 000€**

e-SPACE is an SME Instrument project presenting an innovative solution based on measures correlation between an autonomous ground-based solar sensor and Earth observation data.

Is a solar installation working at its full potential or not? This question is more frequently asked these days either by solar farms operators, venture capitalists willing to invest in renewable energy or companies specialized in operations and maintenance. Comparing irradiance data observed from the ground with data coming from relevant geostationary satellite should provide the answer.

e-SPACE Monitoring aims at delivering PV operators with a permanent PV performance assessment on line service. Through a SAAS platform, operators will access data based on measures correlation between a stand-alone ground-based solar irradiance measurement sensor and satellite data coming from geostationary meteorological satellites completed by Sentinel 4 & 5 satellites and Copernicus services.

By using data analysis algorithms, e-SPACE Monitoring's personalized service will be able to point out discrepancies between the solar data measured on site and the plant's actual solar production. This information will be used by plant operators to set up personalized Key Performance Indicators showing whether a solar installation is working at its full potential or not and improve the Operations & Maintenance of their PV installations.

In the coming years, e-SPACE Monitoring will enable REUNIWATT to take advantage of the tremendous growth of the installed solar base worldwide and resulting PV monitoring market. REUNIWATT has a huge opportunity to market a service that will benefit thousands of solar operators globally and contribute to the development of solar power efficiency.

<https://reuniwatt.com/en/>

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REACT

RENEWABLE ENERGY FOR SELF-SUSTAINABLE ISLAND COMMUNITIES

- > European Program: **Horizon 2020**
Contract Number: **824395**

- > Coordinator: **Veolia company, Spain**

- > Local partner: **The Energy and Processes Laboratory (LE2P) University of Reunion island**

- > Project Duration: **2019 - 2022**

- > **BUDGET**
Total cost: **10 764 405€**
Requested EC Contribution: **8 974 327€**

<https://react2020.eu/>

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REACT main objective is to achieve island energy independency by joining renewable energy sources (RES) and storage, a demand response platform and promote user engagement in a local energy community.

REACT will demonstrate the potential of large-scale deployment of RES and storage assets on geographical islands to bring economic benefits, contribute to the decarbonisation of local energy systems, reduce greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) and improve air quality. To do so, REACT will deliver a scalable and adaptable cloud-based Information and Communications Technology (ICT) platform for RES and storage enabled infrastructures, supporting a holistic cooperative energy management strategy at the community level. REACT will combine an optimal control of community owned energy assets, both conventional and renewable, with cooperative demand response (DR) actions, both explicit and implicit, to maximally exploit the flexibility of energy demand. To achieve this, REACT will leverage on energy production and consumption modelling, grid operation fault detection and diagnostics, multi-carrier supply optimization and optimal energy dispatching, while enabling synergies between different energy networks and micro-grids of island. REACT will deliver effective business models making a synergy of grid- and community-centric approaches for sustainable RES solutions, increased renewable energy exploitation, integrated and digitalised smart grids, and DR programs. Moreover, REACT will provide

a solution that is fully compliant with contemporary regulatory and legal aspects, while respecting the data security and applying suitable data protection measures. REACT will target to enhance the overall energy security of geographical island with an inherent possibility for scale-up and deliver at least 10% energy savings, energy costs savings and GHG emission reduction both by 60%, and at least 50% increase in RES generation and similar reduction in fossil fuel consumption. REACT solution will be validated in 3 demo islands, while replication plans will be made for 5 other "follower" islands across EU, including La Reunion.

RESOR

SUPPORTING ENERGY EFFICIENCY AND RENEWABLE ENERGY IN EUROPEAN ISLANDS AND REMOTE REGIONS

European Program: **INTERREG Europe**

Contract Number: **824395**

Coordinator: **The Vice-Ministry of Industry and Energy of the Canary Islands**

Local partner: **The Regional Council of Reunion Island**

Project Duration: **2018 - 2022**

BUDGET

Total cost: **1 732 924€**

Requested EC Contribution: **1 472 985€**

<https://www.interregeurope.eu/resor/>

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The objective of the project is to support energy efficiency and renewable energy use in businesses of the secondary and tertiary sector of the partner regions by improving current regional policies.

Maximising energy savings and reaching high energy efficiency levels are crucial challenges currently faced by the EU. Remote regions, as those partners in the RESOR project, are characterised by a higher dependence on fossil fuels and general less efficient energy choices and behaviours among citizens and even more among businesses, for whom investment in renewables or energy efficiency are often not a priority or financially feasible. RESOR was thus born as a response to the need for supporting businesses in the adoption of more sustainable energy behaviours and practices. The focus chosen by partners targets remote territories, which on one hand represent less favoured areas of Europe but which, on the other, are often well placed to utilize innovative solutions and attract energy investments.

The aim of the project is to support energy efficiency and renewable energy use in businesses of the secondary and tertiary sector of the partner regions by improving current regional policies. The project activities will envisage an interregional

learning process involving staff from public authorities and representatives of relevant stakeholder groups. This learning process will result in the identification of best practices for the improvement of regional policy instruments supporting energy efficiency and RES use and in the draft of Action Plans to be implemented in each partner region.

TRUST-TV

INCREASE FRIENDLY INTEGRATION OF RELIABLE
PV PLANTS CONSIDERING DIFFERENT
MARKET SEGMENTS

- > European Program: **HORIZON 2020**
Contract Number: **952957**

- > Coordinator: **ACCADEMIA EUROPEA DI
BOLZANO**
Local partner: **REUNIWATT**

- > Project Duration: **September 2020
August 2024**

- > **BUDGET**
Total cost: **12 984 222,50€**
Requested EC Contribution: **9 969 043,63€**

<https://trust-pv.eu/>

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TRUST-PV will demonstrate increase in performance and reliability of PV components and PV systems in large portfolios of distributed and/or utility scale PV.

TRUST-PV will demonstrate increase in performance and reliability of PV components (e.g. module O&M friendly design, inverter enabled O&M solutions, aftermarket coatings, extended testing beyond standard) and PV systems (e.g. more accurate yield models and assessment, data-driven mitigation measures from monitoring and advanced field inspection, reliability of novel system concepts such as floating PV) in large portfolios of distributed and/or utility scale PV. The TRUST-PV results will be tested and demonstrated from fab to field and all data gathered along the value chain will flow into a decision support system platform with enhanced decision-making using AI.

The innovation at component level in TRUST-PV will be driven by the needs of stakeholders operating in a later stage of a PV project, i.e. Asset managers, EPC and O&M operators. TRUST-PV PV modules will thus become O&M friendly and inverter will enable rapid and cost-effective field inspection.

The innovation at system level will fully exploit the digitalisation of the PV sector by linking 3D design with BIM concepts, developing more accurate models for yield assessments, and closing the gap between performance and failure detection through monitoring and field inspection.

The innovation at the point of connection is based on the deployment of tailored strategies for the residential sector (better observability of performance with cost-effective monitoring solution, use of storage to enable renewable energy communities) and the utility sector (e.g. combination of advanced forecasting with storage and regulation through power plant controllers) with the final aim of improving the hosting capacity and increase stability.

Finally, in TRUST-PV we envision a path of circular economy which enhances disposed components/material recovery for further use in the industry, to support progressive steps of plant repowering, aimed at increasing their production and lifetime without requiring additional land.

LEAP-RE

LONG-TERM JOINT EUROPEAN UNION -
AFRICAN UNION RESEARCH AND INNOVATION
PARTNERSHIP ON RENEWABLE ENERGY

European Program: **HORIZON 2020**
Contract Number: **963530**

Coordinator: **LGI sustainable innovation**
Local partner: **Nexa, the regional agency
for development, investment and
innovation in Reunion Island**

Project Duration: **October 2020**
December 2025

BUDGET
Total cost: **32 550 922,44€**
Requested EC Contribution: : **14 952 219€**

 <https://www.leap-re.eu/>

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Sustainable and clean sources of energy are needed to reduce climate change.

The European Green Deal reinforces Europe's commitment to developing and improving renewable energies at home and abroad. In this context, the EU is promoting a renewable energy shift in Africa. The EU-funded LEAP-RE project will create a long-term partnership of African and European stakeholders in government, research and academia, the private sector and civil society. In its mission to develop renewable energy as a sustainable source of energy for all in Africa, the project will work to reduce fragmentation by aligning existing bilateral and multilateral frameworks. It brings together a large-scale consortium of 96 partners from 34 countries and two international organisations.

The LEAP-RE programme aligns with and responds to the AU-EU high-level policies and specific objectives of the CCSE Roadmap. It seeks to create a long-term partnership of African and European stakeholders in a quadruple helix approach: government (programme owners and funding agencies), research and academia, private sector, and civil society. Impact will be sought by creating a framework, methodology, and cooperation model. The aim is to reduce fragmentation by aligning existing bilateral and multilateral frameworks. LEAP-RE establishes and jointly implements research, innovation, and capacity-building activities that respond to the Multi-Annual Roadmaps

(MARs) developed in PRE-LEAP-RE.

The programme opted for a large-scale, inclusive consortium of 96 partners from 34 countries and 2 international organisations, to ensure a broad thematic, geographical and stakeholder coverage, and to demonstrate the feasibility of the collaboration and build trust in view of a long-term partnership addressing the post-2025 period.

LEAP-RE draws on the experience and partnership developed in PRE-LEAP-RE, which conceptualised and developed a framework for long-term, bi-regional cooperation in research, innovation, and capacity building in renewable energies. This partnership is further strengthened by previous collaboration between partners in other projects supporting the EU-Africa HLPD on STI, such as LEAP-Agri, ERAfrica, LEAP4FNSSA, RINEA, and CAAST-Net Plus. Furthermore, the proposal includes a number of R&I partners, 8 individual projects (formalised as Work Packages), which were chosen among expressions of interest received in late 2019.

Earth system Sciences

ACTRIS-2 ◊ ARISE2 ◊ ENVRI PLUS ◊ ATMO-ACCESS

ACTRIS-2

AEROSOLS, CLOUDS, AND TRACE GASES
RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

- > European Program: **Horizon 2020**
Contract Number: **654109**
- > Coordinator: **The National Research Council of Italy**
- > Local partner: **Universe sciences observatory _ University of Réunion Island**
- > Project Duration: **2015 - 2019**
- > **BUDGET**
Total cost: **10 126 485€**
Requested EC Contribution: **9 541 195€**

 <https://www.actris.eu/Home.aspx>

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The European Research Infrastructure for the observation of Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases : ACTRIS serves a vast community of users working on atmospheric research, climate and Earth system and air quality models, satellite retrievals, weather analysis and forecast systems by offering high quality data and research.

ACTRIS-2 addresses the scope of integrating state-of-the-art European ground-based stations for long term observations of aerosols, clouds and short lived gases capitalizing work of FP7-ACTRIS. ACTRIS-2 aims to achieve the construction of a user-oriented RI, unique in the EU-RI landscape.

ACTRIS-2 provides 4-D integrated high-quality data from near-surface to high altitude (vertical profiles and total-column), relevant to climate and air-quality research. ACTRIS-2 develops and implements, in a large network of stations in Europe and beyond, observational protocols that permit harmonization of collected data and their dissemination. ACTRIS-2 offers networking expertise, upgraded calibration services, training of users, trans-national access to observatories and calibration facilities, virtual access to high-quality data products. Through joint research activities, ACTRIS-2 develops new integration tools that produces scientific or technical progresses reusable in infrastructures, thus shaping future observation strategies. Innovation in instrumentation is one of the fundamental building blocks of ACTRIS-2. Associated partnership with SMEs stimulates development of joint-ventures addressing

new technologies for use in atmospheric observations.

Target user-groups in ACTRIS-2 comprise a wide range of communities worldwide. End-users are institutions involved in climate and air quality research, space agencies, industries, air quality agencies. ACTRIS-2 improves systematic and timely collection, processing and distribution of data and results for use in modelling, in particular towards implementation of atmospheric and climate services. ACTRIS-2 invests substantial efforts to ensure long-term sustainability beyond the term of the project by positioning the project in both the Group on Earth (GEO) and the on-going European Strategy Forum Observation on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) contexts, and by developing synergies with national initiatives.

ARISE2

ATMOSPHERIC DYNAMICS RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE IN EUROPE

European Program: **Horizon 2020**
Contract Number: **653980**

Coordinator: **French Alternative
Energies and Atomic Energy
Commission (CEA)**

Local partner: **Universe sciences
observatory _ University of Réunion
Island**

Project Duration: **2015 - 2018**

BUDGET

Total cost: **3 242 382€**
Requested EC Contribution: **2 985 250€**

<http://arise-project.eu/>

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The ARISE2 project is a collaborative infrastructure that provides a new 3D image of atmospheric disturbances in the troposphere, stratosphere and mesosphere.

It has been robustly demonstrated that variations in the circulation of the middle atmosphere influence weather and climate throughout the troposphere all the way to the Earth's surface. A key part of the coupling between the troposphere and stratosphere occurs through the propagation and breaking of planetary-scale Rossby waves and gravity waves. Limited observation of the middle atmosphere and these waves in particular limits the ability to faithfully reproduce the dynamics of the middle atmosphere in numerical weather prediction and climate models. ARISE2 capitalizes upon the work of the EU-funded first ARISE project combining for the first time international networks with complementary technologies such as infrasound, lidar and airglow. This joint network provided advanced data products that started to be used as benchmarks for weather forecast models. The ARISE network also allows enhanced and detailed monitoring of other extreme events in the Earth system such as erupting volcanoes, magnetic storms, tornadoes and tropical thunderstorms. In order to improve the ability of the network to monitor atmospheric dynamics, ARISE2 proposes to extend i) the existing network coverage in Africa and the high latitudes, ii) the altitude range in the stratosphere and

mesosphere, iii) the observation duration using routine observation modes, and to use complementary existing infrastructures and innovative instrumentations. Data is collected over the long term to improve weather forecasting to monthly or seasonal timescales, to monitor atmospheric extreme events and climate change. Compared to the first ARISE project, ARISE2 focuses on the link between models and observations for future assimilation of data by operational weather forecasting models. Among the applications, ARISE2 proposes infrasound remote volcano monitoring to provide notifications to civil aviation. The data portal provides high-quality data and advanced data products to a wide scientific community.

ENVRI PLUS

ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES
PROVIDING SHARED SOLUTIONS
FOR SCIENCE AND SOCIETY

European Program: **Horizon 2020**

Contract Number: **654182**

Coordinator: **The Integrated carbon
observation system European
Research Infrastructure E-consortium**

Local partner: **The Universe sciences
observatory _ University of Réunion
Island**

Project Duration: **2015 - 2019**

BUDGET

Total cost: **14 998 034€**

Requested EC Contribution: **14 683 534€**

ENVRIplus is a Horizon 2020 project bringing together Environmental and Earth System Research Infrastructures, projects and networks together with technical specialist partners to create a more coherent, interdisciplinary and interoperable cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures across Europe.

ENVRIPLUS is a cluster of research infrastructures (RIs) for Environmental and Earth System sciences, built around ESFRI roadmap and associating leading e-infrastructures and Integrating Activities together with technical specialist partners. ENVRIPLUS is driven by 3 overarching goals: 1) favouring cross-fertilization between infrastructures, 2) implementing innovative concepts and devices across RIs, and 3) facilitating research and innovation in the field of environment to an increasing number of users outside the RIs. ENVRIPLUS organizes its activities along a main strategic plan where sharing multi-disciplinary expertise will be most effective. It aims to improve Earth observation monitoring systems and strategies, including actions towards harmonization and innovation, to generate common solutions to many shared information technology and data related challenges, to harmonize policies for access and provide strategies for knowledge transfer amongst RIs. ENVRIPLUS develops guidelines to enhance trans-disciplinary use of data and data-products supported by applied use-cases involving RIs from different domains. ENVRIPLUS coordinates actions to improve communication and

cooperation, addressing Environmental RIs at all levels, from management to end-users, implementing RI-staff exchange programs, generating material for RI personnel, and proposing common strategic developments and actions for enhancing services to users and evaluating the socio-economic impacts. ENVRIPLUS is expected to facilitate structuration and improve quality of services offered both within single RIs and at pan-RI level. It promotes efficient and multi-disciplinary research offering new opportunities to users, new tools to RI managers and new communication strategies for environmental RI communities. The produced solutions, services and other project results are made available to all environmental RI initiatives, thus contributing to the development of a consistent European RI ecosystem.

<https://www.envriplus.eu/>

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ATMO-ACCESS

SOLUTIONS FOR SUSTAINABLE ACCESS
TO ATMOSPHERIC RESEARCH FACILITIES

European Program: **Horizon 2020**

Contract Number: **101008004**

Coordinator: **French National Centre for
Scientific Research**

Local partner: **The University of La Reunion,
Atmospheric and cyclone laboratory**

Project Duration: **April 2021 - March 2025**

BUDGET

Total cost: **14 999 947,89€**

Requested EC Contribution: **14 999 947,89€**

ATMO-ACCESS is the organized response of distributed atmospheric research facilities for developing a pilot for a new model of Integrating Activities.

The project will deliver a series of recommendations for establishing a comprehensive and sustainable framework for access to distributed atmospheric Research Infrastructures (RI), ensuring integrated access to and optimised use of the services they provide. ATMO-ACCESS mobilizes extensive resources in the atmospheric RIs communities to engage into harmonizing access procedures in relation to policies, financial regulations and conditions for access.

It will develop and test innovative modalities of access to facilities and complementary and more advanced services, including digital services, developed as part of cross-RI efforts. ATMO-ACCESS will open physical and remote access to 43 operational European atmospheric research facilities, including ground-based observation stations, simulation chambers, but also mobile facilities and central laboratories that are fundamental elements in distributed RIs. Innovative cross-RI cloud services, addressing the management of data produced via access and the use of new, integrated data products, but also virtual tools for training, are offered through virtual access to RI data centres.

All work in ATMO-ACCESS integrates experiences from past access programs,

thus, synergistically streamlining the work and avoiding duplication of efforts. ATMO-ACCESS will continuously engage with users and with national and international stakeholders to propose optimal conditions for a coherent and effective framework of access that has been sufficiently tested and is supported by the relevant user and stakeholder groups to establish and ensure the long-term sustainability of access with the European RI landscape.

 <https://www.atmo-access.eu/>

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Health & Biotechnology

EUROlinkCAT ◊ MECADISTEM ◊ TASCMAR ◊ ZIKAlliance

EUROlinkCAT

ESTABLISHING A LINKED EUROPEAN COHORT OF CHILDREN WITH CONGENITAL ANOMALIES

- European Program: **Horizon 2020**
Contract Number: **733001**
- Coordinator: **The Queen Mary University of London**
- Local partner: **The University Teaching Hospital of Reunion Island**
- Project Duration: **2017 - 2021**
- BUDGET**
Total cost: **7 348 072€**
Requested EC Contribution: **7 348 072€**

 <https://www.eurolinkcat.eu/>

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The project main objective is to establish a European network of standardised datasets containing information on the mortality, health, educational achievements and needs of children with congenital anomalies.

Over 130,000 children born in Europe every year will have a congenital anomaly (CA; birth defect). These CAs, which are often rare diseases, are a major cause of infant mortality, childhood morbidity and long-term disability.

EUROCAT is an established European network of population-based registries for the epidemiologic surveillance of CAs. EUROlinkCAT will use the EUROCAT infrastructure to support 21 EUROCAT registries in 13 European countries to link their CA data to mortality, hospital discharge, prescription and educational databases. Each registry will send standard aggregate tables and analysis results to a Central Results Repository (CRR) thus respecting data security issues surrounding sensitive data. The CRR will contain standardised summary data and analyses on an estimated 200,000 children with a CA born from 1995 to 2014 up to age 10, enabling hypotheses on their health and education to be investigated at an EU level. This enhanced information will allow optimisation of personalised care and treatment decisions for children with rare CAs.

Registries will be supported in using social media platforms to connect with families who live with CAs in their regions. A novel

sustainable e-forum, "ConnectEpeople", will link these families with local, national and international registries and information resources. ConnectEpeople will involve these families in setting research priorities and ensuring a meaningful dissemination of results.

Findings will provide evidence to inform national treatment guidelines, such as concerning screening programs, to optimise diagnosis, prevention and treatment for these children and reduce health inequalities in Europe. An economic evaluation of the hospitalisation costs associated with CA will be provided.

The CRR and associated documentation, including linkage and standardisation procedures and "ConnectEpeople" forum will be available post-EUROlinkCAT thus facilitating future local and EU level analyses.

MECADISTEM

A NEW AND INNOVATIVE METHOD TO EXTRACT ADIPOSE STROMAL VASCULAR FRACTION: APPLICATION IN POST-PROSTATECTOMY ERECTILE DYSFUNCTION

- European Program: **Horizon 2020**
Contract Number: **855288**
- Coordinator: **STEMCIS SAS**
- Project Duration: **May 2019 - August 2019**
- BUDGET**
Total cost: **71 429€**
Requested EC Contribution: **50 000€**

<https://www.stemcis.com/>

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Erectile dysfunction (ED) remains common following radical prostatectomy. Recent clinical studies have shown that stromal vascular fraction, a therapy made of stem cells that are harvested from the adipose tissue found in our bodies, offers renewed hope.

The EU-funded STEMCIS project developed a unique kit that isolates the adipose cells and regenerates damaged tissues. Building on this work, the MECADISTEM project is developing a single-use kit that includes all the necessary tools to rapidly (less than 30 minutes) extract adipose tissue progenitor cells mechanically. Researchers aim to fast-track development for rapid commercialisation and improved quality of life for both the patient and his partner.

Erectile dysfunction (ED) is a significant and common medical problem which impairs quality of life of men and their partners. ED is a frequent complication after a radical prostatectomy (RP) due to surgical treatment for prostate cancer. For this condition, ED represents a significant unmet medical need, since there is no efficient treatment to repair the cellular damages following a RP. Clinical implementation of stem cell treatment represents a potential candidate for ED treatment after RP. Adult progenitor cells extracted from adipose tissue, called Stromal Vascular Fraction (SVF) have shown promising results in preclinical and clinical studies to treat post-RP ED. STEMCIS has developed a unique kit to isolate the adipose cells which hold

the potential to cure post-prostatectomy ED by regenerating the damaged tissues. MECADISTEM comes in the form of a single-use kit that includes all the tools necessary to simply and rapidly (less than 30 minutes) extract adipose tissue progenitor cells mechanically (grinding, centrifugation, filtration). Compared to the state-of-the-art alternatives using "collagenase (enzymatic) digestion", MECADISTEM does not require the use of enzymes, avoiding the problems and constraints imposed by the use of this enzymatic digestion and offering substantial time and money savings, on both technical and surgical operations. Having validated this methodology in preclinical study, this project is planned to finalise the development and market preparation of this kit. In this Phase 1 Feasibility Study, we aim to evaluate the main milestones of the project from a technical, commercial and financial point of view. Once in the market, MECADISTEM will be used by urologists and surgeons to cure ED in patients following a RP, where the current therapies have not been proven effective. It will secure the growth for STEMCIS, expecting to gain over €12 million in profits, hire 6 new people and reach a ROI of €6.28 from this project after 5 years.

TASCMAR

TOOLS AND STRATEGIES TO ACCESS TO ORIGINAL
BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS FROM CULTIVATION
OF MARINE INVERTEBRATES AND ASSOCIATED
SYMBIONTS

European Program: **Horizon 2020**
Contract Number: **634674**

Coordinator: **The French National Center
for Scientific Research (CNRS)**

Local partner: **The Chemistry Laboratory of
Natural Substances and Food Sciences
University of Reunion Island**

Project Duration: **2015 - 2019**

BUDGET

Total cost: **6 758 453€**
Requested EC Contribution: **6 755 950€**

 www.tascmar.eu

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The main project objective is to develop new tools and strategies to overcome existing bottlenecks in the discovery and application of marine-derived biomolecules.

TASCMAR project aspires to develop new tools and strategies in order to overcome existing bottlenecks in the biodiscovery and industrial exploitation of novel marine derived biomolecules (secondary metabolites and enzymes) with applications in the pharmaceuticals, nutraceuticals, cosmeceuticals and fine chemicals industries. Exploitation of lected and underutilized marine invertebrates and symbionts from mesophotic zone is combined with innovative approaches for the cultivation and extraction of marine organisms from lab to pilot-scale, using the unique prototypes Platotex™ and Zippertex™, both reaching the Technology Readiness Level 7. Thus, marine dedicated cultivation and extraction equipment will be built and validated. These unique improvements will ensure sustainable supply of biomass and promote the production of high added value bioactive marine compounds. An integrated, holistic technological metabolomic approach will be applied, in conjunction with bioactivity profiling, as filtering and bio-prioritisation tools. Moreover, state-of-the-art analytical instrumentation and in-house databases will be employed for the dereplication and characterization of valuable compounds.

A panel of libraries (marine organisms, extracts, pure metabolites and biocatalysts) will be constructed and exploited throughout the project. A focused panel of in-vitro, cell-based, in-ovo and in-vivo bioassays for discovering metabolites with anti-ageing and/or angiogenesis modulating activity will frame the entire work-flow and will reveal the lead compounds. In addition, the catalytic potential of mesophotic symbionts and deriving enzymes candidates will be evaluated in fine chemicals and bioremediation industries. The project activities will be constantly assessed via effective management for their societal, economical and environmental impact in order to find the best compromise between industrial development and sustainable growth.

ZIKAlliance

A GLOBAL ALLIANCE FOR ZIKA VIRUS
CONTROL AND PREVENTION

European Program: **Horizon 2020**

Contract Number: **734548**

Coordinator: **The French National Institute of Health and Medical Research (INSERM^o)**

Local partner: **The PIMIT joint Research group : Infectious Processes in Tropical Island Environments Research Group (Reunion Island)**

Project Duration: **2016 - 2020**

BUDGET

Total cost: **15 684 926€**

Requested EC Contribution: **11 964 209€**

 <https://zikalliance.tghn.org/>

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The project main objective is to investigate clinical, fundamental, environmental and social aspects of ZIKV infection.

ZIKAlliance is a multidisciplinary project with a global «One Health» approach, built on a multi-centric network of clinical cohorts in the Caribbean, Central & South America; research sites in countries where the virus has been or is currently circulating (Africa, Asia, Polynesia) or at risk for emergence (Reunion Island); a strong network of European and Brazilian clinical & basic research institutions; and multiple interfaces with other scientific and public health programmes. ZIKAlliance will address three key objectives relating to (I) impact of Zika virus (ZIKV) infection during pregnancy and short & medium term effects on newborns, (ii) associated natural history of ZIKV infection in humans and their environment in the context of other circulating arboviruses and (iii) building the overall capacity for preparedness research for future epidemic threats in Latin America & the Caribbean. The project will take advantage of large standardised clinical cohorts of pregnant women and febrile patients in regions of Latin America and the Caribbean where the virus is circulating, expanding a pre-existing network established by the IDAMS EU project. It will also benefit of a very strong expertise in basic and environmental sciences, with access to both field work and sophisticated technological infrastructures

to characterise virus replication and physiopathology mechanisms. To meet its 3 key objectives, the scientific project has been organised in 9 work packages, with WP2/3 dedicated to clinical research (cohorts, clinical biology, epidemiology & modelling), WP3/4 to basic research (virology & antivirals, pathophysiology & animal models), WP5/6 to environmental research (animal reservoirs, vectors & vector control), WP7/8 to social sciences & communication, and WP9 to management. The broad consortium set-up allows gathering the necessary expertise for an actual interdisciplinary approach, and operating in a range of countries with contrasting ZIKV epidemiological status.

Social sciences and social innovation

FORWARD ◊ GROW RUP ◊ NEWTS ◊ OCEAN Mètiss

FORWARD

FOSTERING RESEARCH EXCELLENCE IN EU OUTERMOST REGIONS

European Program: **Horizon 2020**

Contract Number: **824550**

Coordinator: **The government of the
Canary Islands**

Local partners: **NEXA, the regional agency
for development, investment and
innovation in Reunion Island ;
the University of Reunion Island**

Project Duration: **2019 - 2021**

BUDGET

Total cost: **4 277 423€**

Requested EC Contribution: **4 277 423€**

 www.forward-h2020.eu

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Forward aims at boosting Research Excellence & Innovation Capacity of the European Outermost Regions and increasing the regions involvement in the European Research Area

The EU has nine Outermost Regions (ORs): Guadeloupe, French Guiana, Martinique, Saint Martin, Réunion, Mayotte, the Canary Islands, and the Azores and Madeira. ORs are an integral part of EU territory but, as Article 349 TFEU recognizes, they differ from the rest of the EU due to their remoteness, their insularity, their small size, their adverse topographical and climatic conditions and their dependence on a limited number of local industries. ORs' participation in Horizon 2020 is inhibited by the fragmentation of the research community due to the geographic isolation but also lack of commitment of research institutions and missing connectivity with excellent partners in Europe and internationally beyond the traditional links with the European mainland of the same country. Therefore, the potential for excellent research activities based on the above described assets remains largely unexploited. The overall objective of the FORWARD project is to improve ORs' excellence in research and their innovation potential to improve their participation in EU research and innovation funded projects and link research activities with territorial development. The project commits the regional governments from the nine ORs in charge of R&I regional policies together with key R&I actors from each region.

FORWARD will perform an initial analysis of R&I ecosystems and, based on these results, it will put in place tailored actions including definition of joint strategy and thematic action plans, capacity building and networking activities, and approaches for connecting research and policy-making.

Based on a multi-actor, multidisciplinary and cross-sectorial approach, the project will also support the collaboration and networking among representatives of the quadruple helix (university, industry, government and civil society) at regional level and with their counterparts from EU Members States and Third Countries.

GROW RUP

ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT AND CAPACITY BUILDING POLICIES FOR BUSINESS CREATION AND GROWTH IN OUTERMOST REGIONS

European Program: **INTERREG Europe**

Coordinator: **The government of the Canary Islands**

Local partner: **The Regional Council of Reunion Island**

Project Duration: **2017 - 2021**

BUDGET

Total cost: **1 169 423€**

Requested EC Contribution: **994 010€**

 www.interregeurope.eu/growrup/

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GROW RUP supports the creation and growth of innovative companies in the field of green and blue economy in the Outermost Regions.

The GROW RUP project intends to promote and support the creation and development of innovative companies specifically in the field of green and blue economy. Small and Medium Size Companies (SME) are responsible for 85% of employment in Europe. Supporting the creation of new SMEs is thus fundamental to counteract unemployment. In ORs in particular, green and blue economy are economic sectors with strong potential for job creation and for the improvement of SME competitiveness.

In this regard, the aim of the project is thus to support the development of new innovative companies in the green and blue economy in partner regions by improving current

regional policies for business creation and growth. The project activities include an interregional learning process involving staff from public authorities and representatives of relevant stakeholder groups. This learning process instand to research in the identification of best practices for the improvement of regional policy instruments supporting entrepreneurship and SME competitiveness and in the draft of Action Plans to be implemented in each partner region.

NEWS

NUDGES FOR ECONOMICS OF WATER TARIFFS

European Program: **Water Joint Programming Initiatives**

Coordinator: **The Centre of Economics and Management of the Indian Ocean (CEMOI) _ University of Reunion Island**

Project Duration: **2019 - 2022**

BUDGET

Total cost: **1 190 916€**

Requested EC Contribution: **535 385€**

 www.waterjpi.eu/joint-calls/joint-call-2018-waterworks-2017/booklet/news-1

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The research program addresses the issue of household water demand management.

Prima facie, it aims to provide a socio-economic assessment of green nudging policies, focusing on water consumption controlling and proper understanding of the charging system by the households, taking into account adjustments in the pricing policy that nudges may generate (in view of their effects on water demand functions). From an operational point of view, it consists in developing a micro-simulation model, based on econometric estimates of household water demands, to assess the socio-economic returns of mix policies, combining nudges and pricing instruments, and identify financially sustainable DSM (demand-side management) policies to improve current water utility tariffs.

The program is designed around various methodologies. The effects of nudges on household water consumptions are examined through the realization of controlled experiments, in the lab and in the field. Randomized controlled trials are performed in Gijon (Spain), Saint Paul (Reunion Island - France) and Sfax (Tunisia). Econometric estimations of residential water demand are carried out to measure basic water needs of the households, price-sensitivities of demand and perceived prices of water. Econometric exercises are implemented before and after the nudging campaigns, in order to infer the effects of BIs (behavioral interventions) on the latter

three factors and identify the transmission channels through which nudges modify the water demand functions of the households. This knowledge about the water demand functions, as provided by econometric analysis, combined with databases used their estimation enables (i) to assess the socio-economic performance of the tariff; (ii) to infer the effects of nudges on this socio-economic performance; (iii) to identify optimal policies, according to well-defined decision criteria for local public decision-makers, in various analytical and regulatory frameworks. This evaluation process is carried out through a scoreboard and the use of appropriate indicators in accordance with the objectives of EU Water Framework Directive (affordability, incentive character of pricing, equity, economic welfare and quality of funding). In fine, all of these elements articulate to construct a DST (decision support tool) that can be used to inform decision-making about Water Utility DSM policy.

OCEAN Mètiss

MARINE SPATIAL PLANNING TOOLS ADAPTED TO REGIONAL AND LOCAL SCALES TO HELP BOOST ECONOMY WHILE PRESERVING THE RICH BIODIVERSITY.

European Program: **European Maritime and Fisheries Fund**

Coordinator: **The Regional Council of Reunion Island**

Local partner: **The Prefecture of Réunion Island Prefecture of Réunion, The University of Reunion Island, The Indian Ocean Commission**

Project Duration: **2018 - 2021**

BUDGET

Total cost: **1 204 014€**

Requested EC Contribution: **963 211€**

 www.oceanmetiss.re

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OCEAN METISS, aims at defining a blue strategy for Réunion Island and to contribute to the development of Integrated Maritime Spatial Planning in the South-West Basin of the Indian Ocean.

The Ocean Metiss project is a joint action presented by the Regional Council of Réunion Island as a local government in the quality of project coordinator, and the Prefect of the Région Réunion as State Representative, jointly sharing the responsibility of territorial spatial planning, and of the definition of a sustainable strategy for the economic development in the South-Western Indian Ocean Area (SWIO). The project is also supported by the intergovernmental organisation of the Indian Ocean State Islands (Mauritius, Comoros, Madagascar and Seychelles).

on existing factors impacting the local economies and ecosystem (fish stocks, as well as other maritime resources such as renewable energies), and to evaluate the potentials offered by the large maritime zone to boost the economic development, by preserving the rich tropical biodiversity of the concerned territories.

The Ocean Metiss MSP project will allow to elaborate a new, horizontal and cross sectoral planning tool, aimed to guide public policies to create a sustainable, integrated, long-term strategy for the SWIO Basin.

The main goal of the project is to create a complete, integrated status report

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